

ENERGY ABSORPTION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR CRASHWORTHY STRUCTURES

by

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ABSTRACT

U.S. Army helicopters are designed to meet stringent crash resistance requirements as specified in Mil-Std-1290 which defines the various crash scenarios that must be survivable for the occupants. The next generation military helicopters will make an extensive use of advanced composite materials in primary structure applications. Therefore, it is imperative to develop an indepth understanding of the energy absorption process of composites. The U.S. Army Aerostructures Directorate/NASA crash energy absorption research program has primarily focused on understanding energy absorption of composite materials and the development of energy absorbing subfloor concepts.

Crash energy-absorption processes of composite materials have been studied. The cause/effect relationship between changes in material property and specimen architecture and their effect on energy-absorption capability have been defined. Several energy absorbing subfloor beam concepts have been experimentally evaluated. Composite beams have been developed to have significantly more energy-absorption capability than comparable metal designs. A simple and accurate method of predicting the energy-absorption capability of subfloor beams has been developed.

INTRODUCTION

All new U.S. Army helicopter fuselages are designed to meet the vehicle crashworthiness requirements as defined by Mil-Std-1290. This single design requirement is the principal structural design criteria for the fuselage and has encouraged developments in several new technologies during the last decade. The next generation helicopter will be fabricated using a high percentage of advanced fiber reinforced polymeric matrix composite material in primary structure. Therefore, a detail understanding of the crash energy-absorption characteristics of composite materials must be developed. The primary objective of this research program is to develop sufficient technology to enable the design of energy absorbing composite fuselage structure to be performed in a manner consistent with current composite structural design practices.

This paper presents a limited summary of certain facets of the U.S. Army

Aerostructures Directorate/NASA research conducted on the crash energy absorption capability of composite material. Included is a discussion of the crushing characteristics of tube specimens fabricated from composite materials and how certain material and architectural properties effect the energy-absorption process. Circular and square cross section tube specimens were used to investigate the effects of material and architectural variables and how the material response is related to the structural response of the beam. Experimental energy-absorption studies of subfloor beam structure are also presented. A method of predicting the energy-absorption capability of composite subfloor beams is also presented.

COMPOSITE MATERIAL

Composite materials and structures fabricated from composites absorb energy in modes that are considerably different than metallic materials and structures. To efficiently utilize composite materials in energy-absorption applications the different crushing modes and mechanisms must be understood. Composite materials offer the potential to tailor the mechanical response by means of material property (fiber and matrix stiffness and failure strain) variables and architectural (ply orientation, stacking sequence, hybridization, fiber volume fraction and specimen geometry) variables. These variables affect the mechanical response of the laminate and logic suggests they also effect the energy-absorption capability. In this section a description of the crushing modes exhibited by composite materials are presented along with a discussion of the effect of material property variables and architectural variables on energy-absorption capability.

In the following discussion the specific sustained crushing stress of composite tubes and beams is employed as a measure of energy-absorption capability. Specific sustained crushing stress is the sustained crushing load divided by the product of the density and cross sectional area of the specimen.

Crushing Modes

Four different crushing modes and combinations of the four modes have been identified for composite materials, [1 and 2]. These four modes are 1) local buckling, 2) transverse shearing, 3) brittle fracturing, and 4) lamina bending, as shown in figure 1. The local buckling mode is similar to that exhibited by metallic materials. This crushing mode has been demonstrated by both ductile (Kevlar) and brittle (graphite and glass) fiber-reinforced composites. Ductile fiber composites exhibit the local buckling crushing mode, exclusively, regardless of the matrix material. Ductile fibers plastically deform at the buckle site along the compression side of the buckled fibers. The fibers can also split into small fibrils along the tension side of the buckled fibers. Fiber plasticity and splitting are the mechanisms that keep the specimen together after it is crushed which is called post-crushing integrity. Brittle fiber composites only exhibit the local buckling crushing mode for ply orientations that have interlaminar stresses which are small relative to the strength of the matrix and have matrices with high failure strain and low stiffness. The combination of a high failure strain/low stiffness matrix with certain ply orientations reduces or prevents interlaminar cracking from occurring in the crushing process. If the interlaminar cracks are eliminated, the tube crushes in the local buckling mode or fails catastrophically.

The brittle fracturing, lamina bending, and transverse shearing modes are

exhibited exclusively by brittle fiber reinforced composites. These crushing modes are a function of the mechanical properties of the constituent materials. Generally, one or multiple interlaminar cracks are formed through the thickness of the composite. The number, location, and length of the cracks are a function of specimen architecture and the constituent material properties. The interlaminar cracks form lamina bundles which can be thought of as columns. As the load is applied the interlaminar cracks grow until the column buckles and either the edges of the column are sheared away forming a conical shaped cross section (transverse shearing mode), fractured (brittle fracturing mode), or bent (lamina bending mode).

Debris size of crushed material (characteristic crushing length) is a qualitative measure of energy-absorption efficiency. The characteristic crushing length of specimens that exhibit transverse shearing mode, brittle fracturing mode, lamina bending mode, and local buckling mode are on the order of a lamina thickness, a laminate thickness, 10-100 laminate thicknesses and 10-50 laminate thicknesses, respectively. The smaller the characteristic length the greater the energy-absorption efficiency. This ordering of energy-absorption crushing efficiency is applicable only for specimens of the same material. Different materials have different energy-absorption potentials. A material with a higher energy-absorption potential can have a greater energy-absorption capability in a less efficient crushing mode than a material with a lower energy-absorption potential that crushes in a more efficient mode.

Effect of Material Properties

Fiber and Matrix Failure Strain

A series of studies, [3 and 4], were performed to determine the effect of fiber and matrix failure strain on energy-absorption capability of graphite reinforced composites. These studies were conducted using low failure strain (T300), and intermediate failure strain (AS4) fibers with low failure strain (934) and intermediate failure strain (5245) epoxy matrices. Based upon the results of these studies, as shown in figure 2, composite materials composed of low and intermediate failure strain fibers and matrices (T300/934, AS4/934, T300/5245, and AS4/5245) generally exhibit an increase in energy-absorption capability as failure strain increased. As the failure strain of the reinforcement increased the energy stored prior to failure of the lamina bundles also increases, hence, an increase in energy-absorption capability. Similarly, as matrix failure strain increased the length of the interlaminar crack decreased resulting in a higher buckling load for the lamina bundle and greater energy-absorption capability. The energy-absorption trends for the low and intermediate failure strain material is consistent with mechanical response trends of these composites.

Similar studies were conducted using Kevlar-49 in 934 and 974 matrices to determine the effect of matrix failure strain on the energy-absorption capability of a ductile fiber reinforced composite material. The 974 matrix is an intermediate failure strain material. Based upon tests a 5 to 15 percent decrease in energy-absorption capability occurred as matrix failure strain increased. The decrease in energy-absorption capability is related to a reduction in matrix stiffness at high stresses. The reduction in matrix stiffness reduced the lateral support to the fibers which resulted in a lower buckling load of the lamina bundles.

Effect of Fiber Stiffness

The effects of fiber stiffness, [4], on the energy-absorption capability was evaluated for brittle fiber reinforcements using T300, P55, and P75 graphite fibers in a common matrix (934). It is difficult in studies of this type to isolate the effects of a single property on energy-absorption capability. In this study the effects of fiber stiffness are studied, however, the fibers have significantly different failure strains. The failure strain of the T300, P55, and P75 graphite fibers are 0.012, 0.005, and 0.004, respectively.

Figure 3 shows that energy-absorption capability decreased nonlinearly with increasing fiber stiffness. Difference in energy absorption between material systems are proportional to the difference in fiber failure strain. This proportionality between energy absorption and fiber failure strain can be readily seen upon examining the energy-absorption trends of ply orientations where fibers are principally oriented in the direction of the applied load such as $[0/\pm 15]_4$. These results suggest that energy-absorption capability is less sensitive to changes in fiber stiffness than to fiber failure strain, provided the different materials crush in the same mode.

Effect of Matrix Stiffness

Conventional thermoset matrices (e.g. epoxies) with stiffnesses of 3.4 GPa generally have failure strains of between 0.01 ϵ and 0.025 ϵ and linear or near linear stress-strain response. As matrix stiffness decreases to 1.7 GPa failure strains typically increase to between 0.10 ϵ and 0.15 ϵ and the stress-strain response can become highly nonlinear.

As previously discussed matrix failure strain significantly affects the crushing response of brittle fiber reinforced composite material, whereas its contribution seems less significant with ductile fiber composites. Formulating a series of tests to quantify the effects of matrix stiffness with no other significant confounding factors is difficult. However, based upon observation and a general understanding of the crushing process, the following statements seem reasonable. Matrix stiffness contributes on the order of 1 percent to the bending stiffness of the lamina bundles and therefore has minimal effects on energy absorption for materials that exhibit a transverse shearing or brittle fracturing mode. Materials that exhibit the lamina bending crushing mode can be affected more significantly. Changes in matrix stiffness affects the end fixity boundary condition of the lamina bundle which changes its buckling load and hence its energy-absorption capability. Reduced matrix stiffness can lower fiber microbuckling load which, in turn, can change crushing modes of brittle fiber composites from the transverse shearing, brittle fracturing or lamina bending modes to the local buckling mode. Changes in matrix stiffness has a limited effect on energy-absorption capability of composite materials with ductile fiber reinforcements. Composite materials with ductile fibers crush in a local buckling mode. The matrix provides lateral stability to the reinforcing fibers, analogous to a beam on an elastic foundation. The buckling load of the fiber (beam) is proportional to the matrix stiffness (foundation).

Effect of Specimen Architecture

Effects of Ply Orientation

Ply orientation is one of the most important variables available to the composite structural designer to tailor the mechanical response of a

composite laminate. The stiffness and strength of a laminate is a direct function of the ply orientation. However, this relationship for energy absorption is not as well defined. Depending upon the mechanical properties of the fiber and matrix, the effects of ply orientation on the crushing response may be significantly different than the effects on the mechanical response.

Tests were conducted, [1], on $[0/\pm\theta]_4$, T300/934 (Gr/E), E-G1/934 (G1/E), and K/934 (K/E) specimens. As shown in figure 4, the energy-absorption trends for the different materials were quite different. As the ply angle increased the energy absorption of the Gr/E material decreased. This trend is consistent with the general mechanical response of composites. However, the opposite trend occurred for the G1/E and K/E material. Energy-absorption capability generally increased with increasing ply angle for the G1/E and K/E material. The difference in energy-absorption trends can be explained by examination of the crushing modes.

The Gr/E specimens crushed in a brittle fracturing mode while the G1/E and K/E specimens crushed in a lamina bending and a local buckling mode, respectively. As previously discussed, if a material can be made to crush in the brittle fracturing mode, as exhibited by the Gr/E, it is generally a more efficient energy-absorption mode than the lamina bending or the local buckling modes. These energy-absorption trends can be related to the constituent properties of the fiber and matrix.

In the case of the Gr/E specimens the matrix is sufficiently stiff and has sufficient failure strain to stabilize the axially oriented graphite fibers in the crushing process. Therefore, the crushing load, hence energy-absorption capability, is a function of axial stiffness. As the bias ply orientation exceeds 45 degrees the bias plies provide lateral support to the axially oriented fibers. That is, the bias plies help the matrix to stabilize the axial fibers. As the ply orientation of the bias plies increased between 60 and 90 degrees the axial stiffness decreased but the increased lateral support to the axially oriented fibers resulted in a relatively constant energy-absorption capability. As bias ply angle increased from between 45 and 90 degrees the characteristic crushing length decreased.

The high elongation capability of the G1 fiber in predominantly uniaxial oriented specimens is not adequately stabilized by the matrix and a less efficient energy-absorption mode (lamina bending) is produced. The crushing response of G1/E specimens with ply orientations of predominantly uniaxial fibers are controlled by the matrix properties and not the axial stiffness of the specimens. As the bias plies become more circumferentially oriented the energy-absorption capability increased even though the axial stiffness decreased. As the bias ply angle increased to approximately 60 degrees the bias plies began to provide lateral stability to the axial fibers. Further increase in circumferential fiber orientation provided no additional support to the axial fibers and the energy-absorption response was a function of axial stiffness and decreased.

A similar crushing scenario as described for the energy-absorption response of G1/E specimens can be applied to the K/E specimens. In this case however, the crushing mode of the K/E specimens is a local buckling mode because of the plastic compression behavior of the Kevlar fibers.

Effects of Specimen Geometry and Scaleability

The geometry (i.e., characteristic dimension, wall thickness, and cross-sectional shape) of tube specimens can significantly effect energy-absorption capability. Understanding the affects of specimen geometry provides insight into the energy-absorption capability of complex structure such as subfloor beam structure.

A series of studies, [5 and 6], were conducted using circular and square cross section tube specimens fabricated with Gr/E and K/E. Tube ply orientations were $[\pm 45]_N$. This ply orientation is used in typical subfloor beam structure. The diameters of circular cross section tubes were between 1.27 cm and 10.16 cm. Square cross section tube widths were between 1.27 cm and 7.62 cm. The number of ± 45 ply pairs (N) was between 2 and 24 resulting in internal diameter-to-wall thickness (D/t) ratios of 1.4 to 125 and width to-wall thickness (W/t) ratios of between 6 and 125. The energy-absorption trends for the Gr/E circular cross section tube specimens and square cross section tubes K/E are shown in figures 5 and 6, respectively.

The energy-absorption capability of Gr/E tubes is a nonlinear function of tube D/t and W/t ratio. All circular cross section Gr/E tubes exhibited a progressive brittle fracturing crushing mode while the square cross section Gr/E tubes exhibited a lamina bending mode. Each diameter tube produced a different nonlinear response. A reduction in tube D/t ratio results in an increase in energy absorption. This increase in energy absorption is related to a reduction in interlaminar cracking in the crushed region of the tube.

The K/E circular and square cross section tubes also exhibited a nonlinear energy-absorption response as a function of tube D/t or W/t ratio, figure 6. Unlike the Gr/E tubes the K/E test results do not show a different energy-absorption response as a function of different tube inside diameter or width. When crushed, all K/E tubes, exhibited the characteristic local buckling crushing mode. The buckle wave length varied with tube geometry (tube diameter or width and wall thickness).

In the present study tube specimens were geometrically scaled by proportionally changing tube inside diameter or width and wall thickness. The test results suggest the energy-absorption capability of Gr/E tubes are not generally geometrically scaleable while the energy-absorption capability of K/E tubes were scaleable.

COMPOSITE SUBFLOOR BEAM CONCEPTS

This research effort has primarily focused upon energy absorbing subfloor beam structure. Four different subfloor beam concepts have been evaluated; sandwich, sine-wave and two integrally stiffened concepts. In this section the relative energy-absorption capabilities of the different concepts will be discussed. A comparison of the energy-absorption trends of the beams will be compared with the material response based upon tube tests. Finally a method to predict the energy-absorption capability of composite subfloor beams is presented.

Energy Absorbing Subfloor Beam Concepts

Four different beam concepts, [7], were evaluated in this research program. These concepts, as depicted in figure 7, are the honeycomb sandwich, sine-wave, circular cross section tube stiffened, and rectangular cross section

tube stiffened beams. The sandwich beams evaluated were fabricated using Nomex honeycomb core co-cured to K/E woven fabric face sheets oriented at ± 45 degrees. Different through-the-thickness stitching concepts were also evaluated in this study. The sandwich beams were not as efficient energy absorbers as the other concepts.

Sine-wave beams were evaluated using many different materials, material forms, hybridization, ply orientations and geometries (D/t). The sine-wave concepts were tangent half tube (included angles of 180 degrees) designs. A limited number of results will be presented. The sine-wave beams energy-absorption trends are similar to those trends found for circular cross section tube specimens. The effects of beam geometry for K/E beams is compared with tube data in figure 8. The agreement between beam and tube results is excellent. The crushing modes of the beams were similar to the crushing modes of comparable tube specimens. The sine-wave beam concept is potentially the most efficient energy absorbing concept evaluated in this research program. The higher energy-absorption potential is because curved sections are more efficient energy absorbers than flat sections.

Both circular and rectangular tube stiffened beams were evaluated. Beams were fabricated from Gr/E, K/E and 6061-T6 aluminum. Ply orientations of all composite beams were $[(\pm 45)_n]_S$. Beam thicknesses were comparable for composite and aluminum beams. Stiffened beams of different geometries were evaluated to compare energy-absorption trends with results from tube data. Figure 9 depicts representative test results for these beam concepts. For comparable geometry beams the Gr/E beams had higher energy-absorption capability than either the K/E or the aluminum beams. Energy-absorption capability as a function of beam geometry for both Gr/E and K/E was consistent with that determined from tube tests. That is, as D/t or W/t increases energy-absorption capability decreases. The crushing modes of the beams were also consistent with the modes of tube specimens of the same material.

Method of Predicting Energy Absorption Capability

The previous sections of this report conclusively demonstrated that crushing characteristics and energy-absorption trends of beams are similar to that exhibited by tube specimens. These results suggest that the energy-absorption capability of a beam can be predicted using tube data.

Upon observing this similarity of crushing modes a hypothesis was formulated, [8], for predicting the energy-absorption capability of structural elements. The hypothesis is: The crash energy-absorption capability of a structural element is the sum of the weighted average of the energy-absorption capability of its characteristic elements. Mathematically, in terms of the specific sustained crushing stress (σ/ρ) , this can be expressed as:

$$\sigma/\rho_{S.E.} = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{A_{iC.E.}}{A_{S.E.}} * \sigma/\rho_{iC.E.} \quad (1)$$

The terms $A_{iC.E.}$ and $A_{S.E.}$ are the cross-sectional areas of the i^{th} characteristic element (C.E.) and the structural element (S.E.), respectively. The $(\sigma/\rho)_{iC.E.}$ and $(\sigma/\rho)_{S.E.}$ are the specific sustained crushing stress of the i^{th} characteristic element and the

structural element, respectively.

This hypothesis assumes the structure will crush prior to catastrophically failing. Other requirements for the applicability of this hypothesis pertain to the commonality of architecture between specimen and structure and commonality of material. That is, the tube specimens must have the same diameter to thickness or width to thickness ratio as the characteristic element of the beam, the same ply orientation and stacking sequence, and have the same material form (e.g., tape, woven fabric, braided, filament wound).

The energy-absorption capability of sine-wave and circular and rectangular cross section tube stiffened beams were determined through test and predicted using equation 1 and circular and square cross section tube test data, [5 and 6]. Differences between prediction and experiment were less than 7 percent.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The energy-absorption capability and crushing modes of composite materials and structures has been evaluated through an extensive test program. The crushing modes and energy-absorption characteristics of beams are similar to those exhibited by tubular specimens of similar material and architecture. The crushing mechanisms have been determined and can be directly related to the mechanical properties of the constituent material and specimen architecture. Ply orientation, fiber and matrix failure strain and specimen geometry significantly effect the energy-absorption capability of composite material. Several energy absorbing beam concepts have been evaluated. Composite beams were determined to have higher energy-absorption capability than comparable metallic beams. A simple and accurate method of predicting the energy-absorption capability of composite structural beams has been developed. The prediction method is based upon the energy-absorption capability of its characteristic elements, which can be determined using tubular composite specimens.

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Figure 1. Four crushing modes of composite tubes.

Figure 2. Effect of fiber failure strain on the energy absorption of graphite reinforced composite material.

Figure 3. Effects of fiber stiffness on energy absorption of $[0/\pm\theta]_4$ graphite/epoxy composite material.

Figure 4. The effects of ply orientation on energy-absorption capability of Gr/E, Gl/E and K/E composite material.

Figure 5. The effects of D/t ratio on the energy absorption of $[\pm 45]_n$ Gr/E tubes.

Figure 6. Energy-absorption capability of square K/E tubes.

Figure 7. Energy-absorption beam concepts.

Figure 8. Effects of D/t ratio on the energy absorption of $[\pm 45]_n$ K/E tubes and sine-wave beams.

Figure 9. Energy-absorption of rectangular tube stiffened beams.